

Removal of copper(II) from water using SrWO₄ — A photocatalytic process

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Manuscript received 10 August 2007, revised 7 January 2008, accepted 8 January 2008

Abstract : Photocatalytic removal of copper(II) over semiconductor SrWO₄ was carried out. The progress of reaction was observed spectrophotometrically. The effect of variation of different parameters like pH, concentration of copper(II), amount of photocatalyst, light intensity etc. on the rate of reaction was observed. A tentative mechanism for this reaction has been proposed.

Keywords : Photocatalyst, reduction, copper(II), semiconductor.

Introduction

Metal ions are generally not degradable. They have infinite life time and built up their concentrations in food chains to toxic level. In today's industrialized society we are living in an environment with a multitude of potentially harmful toxic metal ions. In contrast, the demand of metals has increased significantly with the development of industry. Therefore waste metal removal can potentially resolve two issues : metal pollution prevention and simultaneously, resource conservation.

Trace amount of metal ions from waste water were separated using Alizarin Red S bounded on polyurethane foam by Moawed¹. Photocatalytic reduction of chromium in aqueous solution by Fe³⁺ doped TiO₂ nanoparticles were carried out by Thakare and Jugele². Troupis *et al.*³ studied the photocatalytic reduction and recovery of copper by polyoxometalates. An investigation of TiO₂ photocatalysis for the treatment of water contaminated with metal and organic chemicals was carried out by Prairie *et al.*⁴. Whang and Zhuang⁵ have investigated photocatalytic reduction of pollutant Hg^{II} ions on doped WO₃ dispersion.

Copper is an essential nutrients to all plants and animals. The effluents released from industries like chlor-alkali, electroplating industries, ferrous and non ferrous mining and metallurgy, paints and dyes industries, petroleum refineries, explosives etc. causes serious damages to life. Excessive intake of copper causes hemolysis, hepatotoxic and nephrotoxic effects, tuberculosis and carcinoma. Therefore the present study was undertaken which deals with the photocatalytic reduction of Cu^{II} in aqueous

solution over SrWO₄ powder.

Results and discussion

The photocatalytic reduction of CuSO₄ was observed by AAS at wavelength 324.8 nm. The results of a typical run are given in Table 1 and represented graphically in Fig. 1. It has been observed that plot of log (concentration) vs time (min) is linear, which indicates that this photocatalytic reduction follows pseudo first order kinetics. The rate constant is calculated by

$$k = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$$

It was observed that the rate of reduction is about ten

Table 1. Typical run.

Copper sulphate = 5.10 ppm, temp. = 303 K, pH = 6.5, SrWO₄ = 0.3 g, λ_{max} = 324.8 nm, intensity of light = 54.0 mW cm⁻²

Time (min)	Concn. in dark [C'] (ppm)	Concn. in presence of light [C] (ppm)	1 + log C'	1 + log C
0	5.10	5.10	1.7076	1.7076
30	4.85	2.92	1.6857	1.4654
60	4.62	2.54	1.6646	1.4052
90	4.50	1.97	1.6532	1.2948
120	4.38	1.57	1.6415	1.1955
150	4.25	1.22	1.6284	1.0864
180	4.12	1.07	1.6149	1.0273
210	3.95	0.85	1.5966	0.9318
240	3.87	0.71	1.5877	0.8522
270	3.82	0.54	1.5821	0.7336

$$k' = 0.169 \times 10^{-6} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}, k = 1.267 \times 10^{-6} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}.$$

Fig. 1. Typical run.

times faster in light as compared to dark. The rate constant are $0.169 \times 10^{-6} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$ and $1.267 \times 10^{-6} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$ in dark and light respectively. Further it is observed that there is no change in concentration in absence of semiconductor. This clearly suggested the effect of light on reduction and so photocatalytic reaction was carried out in present investigations.

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH on the rate of reduction of Cu^{II} was studied in the pH range 2.5–7.5; because above the pH = 7.5 precipitation of copper was observed. The results are presented graphically in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Effect of pH : copper sulphate = 5.10 ppm, temp. = 303 K, $\text{SrWO}_4 = 0.30 \text{ g}$, intensity of light = 54.0 mW cm^{-2} , $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 324.8 \text{ nm}$.

It was observed that with the increase in pH, rate of reduction increases. After attaining maximum value (pH 6.5), rate decreases. The optimum value was obtained for pH = 6.5. It is established that surface properties of semiconductor are responsible for photocatalytic process⁶

The hole generated by semiconductor creates H^+ ions in the solution from water. These protons are utilized by dissolved oxygen in solution.

These two reactions counter balance each other to a particular extent. The surface charge on the semiconductor-electrolyte interface will play a major role in deciding the fate of this photocatalytic reduction^{6,7}. The surface charge on semiconductor is responsible for transfer of electrons to Cu^{II} converting it into Cu^{I} . The surface charge on semiconductor favors the reduction when it is positive. This surface charge depends on the pH of the solution being positive in acidic media and negative in alkaline media. After a particular pH net charge on semiconductor surface becomes zero and is called point of zero discharge (PZC)⁹.

When the pH of the solution is low, reaction (i) dominates and reduction of Cu^{II} takes place. As the pH is raised reaction (ii) starts dominating the reaction (i), so that there will be an additional decrease in the amount of H^+ ions and hence the decrease in rate of photocatalytic degradation of Cu^{II} . The reduction of Cu^{II} to its lower oxidation state will also adversely affect the value of PZC and thus it will add to the lowering in the rate of reaction.

Effect of copper(II) concentration :

In the present study the concentration of copper sulphate varies between range 1.50–8.42 ppm. The effect of change in concentration of Cu^{II} on the rate of reaction was observed, keeping all other factors identical. The results are reported in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Effect of copper sulphate concentration : pH = 6.5, temp. = 303 K, $\text{SrWO}_4 = 0.30 \text{ g}$, intensity of light = 54.0 mW cm^{-2} , $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 324.8 \text{ nm}$.

It was observed that as the concentration of copper sulphate increases, the rate of reaction increases. After attaining a maximum value (5.10 ppm), decrease in the rate of reaction was observed. It is due to the fact that electrons available for reduction were consumed and then further addition of Cu^{II} works only as colour imparting factor. This colour works as filter for incident light and the intensity reaching to semiconductor surface is reduced.

Effect of amount of SrWO₄ :

The effect of amount of photocatalyst on the rate of photocatalytic reduction of copper(II) was observed by taking different amounts of semiconductor, keeping all other factors constant. The results are graphically presented in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Effect of amount of SrWO₄ : copper sulphate = 5.10 ppm, temp. = 303 K, pH = 6.5, intensity of light = 54.0 mW cm⁻², λ_{max} = 324.8 nm.

The rate of photocatalytic reduction of Cu^{II} increases with increasing the amount of photocatalyst. After a certain amount of semiconductor (0.30 g), the rate of photocatalytic degradation became constant. Any further increase in amount of semiconductor showed no increase in the rate of reaction.

It can be explained on the basis that as the amount of semiconductor is increased, more particles are available for excitation and there is greater possibility of electron-hole pair generation on exposure to light. This results into a corresponding increase in the rate of reaction. After a certain amount reached (0.30 g), the bottom of the reaction vessel is almost covered and now any addition of semiconductor does not increase the exposed area, rather it only adds to the thickness of the layer of semiconductor at the bottom of the reaction vessel. Hence saturation like behavior is observed. It was confirmed by the fact that as vessel size is changed, value of *k* changes and as solution is stirred, rate increases due to increase in num-

ber of particle exposed to light.

Effect of light intensity :

The intensity of light reaching to the semiconductor is varied by placing reaction vessel at different places beneath the lamp. The results are presented in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Effect of light intensity : copper sulphate = 5.10 ppm, temp. = 303 K, pH = 6.5, SrWO₄ = 0.30 g, λ_{max} = 324.8 nm.

It has been observed that the rate of photocatalytic reaction increases with increasing light intensity. It is attributed to the fact that more electron-hole pair will be generated due to an increased number of photons striking the semiconductor surface with an increase in the intensity of light. Therefore more electrons will be available for reduction, resulting into the increase in rate of reaction.

Mechanism :

On the basis of the observed experimental data, the following tentative mechanism has been proposed for the photocatalytic reduction of copper(II).

In the first step, the semiconductor is excited by the absorption of light of an appropriate wavelength. An electron from the valence band of the semiconductor jumps into its conduction band, leaving behind a hole. This hole is utilized by the water molecule to generate oxygen and H⁺ ions. These H⁺ ions and dissolved oxygen in solution are reduced by two electrons to form hydrogen peroxide, which slowly degrades. In the last step copper(II) accepts two electrons from conduction band of the

semiconductor and reduces to its metallic state. This reduction of Cu^{II} to Cu is also clearly indicated by light reddish brown coloured deposition on the semiconductor. In acidic medium reaction (iv) dominates and thus production of more electrons reduces more Cu^{II} substrate increasing the k value. As the pH is raised, reaction (v) starts dominating resulting into decrease in rate of reduction.

The photocatalytic reduction of metal ions from their higher oxidation state to lower oxidation state will not only make the industrial effluents less toxic, but, in some cases it provides an effective way to recover such metals.

Experimental

Semiconducting powder SrWO_4 was prepared via a precipitation reaction between SrCl_2 and Na_2WO_4 ¹⁰. The precipitate was washed with distilled water for several times and dried. Stock solution of copper sulphate was prepared in doubly distilled water. The photocatalytic reduction of copper sulphate was observed by taking 100 mL solution (5.10 ppm) in a 150 mL beaker and 0.30 g of strontium tungstate was added to it. Irradiation was carried out by keeping whole assembly exposed to 1000 W halogen lamp (Okano, light intensity 54.0 mW cm^{-2}). The intensity of light at various distances from the lamp was measured with the help of a solarimeter (Surya Mapi Model CEL201). A water filter was used to cut out thermal radiation. The pH of the solution was measured with a digital pH meter (Systronics Model 324). The desired pH of the solution was adjusted by the addition of previously standardized sulphuric acid and sodium hydroxide

solution. The progress of the photocatalytic reaction was observed by taking absorbance at regular time intervals using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Varian AA240FS Model).

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to M/s. Hindusthan Zinc Limited, Process Control Laboratory to provide instrumental facility and Prof. S. C. Ameta, Dean, P. G. Studies, MLSU, Udaipur for his kind support.

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